

THE INSTITUTE OF CONTRACTS AND DEALS IN CIVIL LAW: COMPARATIVE-LEGAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract. In a period of transition to free market relations, the socio - economic system is being enriched by a specific change in the legal status of subjects of civil law and the nature of the relations that arise between them and a new content. This, in turn, necessitates the adoption of laws aimed at Legal Regulation of relations that arise between subjects of civil law and their regular improvement. Therefore, the main purpose of this article is to comment on the concepts of contract and deal concluded between citizens in civil law, as well as to analyze the concepts of contract and deal in legal terms.

Keywords: Civil Code, Law, Civil Law, contract, deal, types, differences, similarities.

Civil law was considered one of the independent and important branches of any developed legal system, which arose as the initial foundation of the legal system that was formed in the ancient Roman state. All actions committed in this period, initially regulated by civil legal norms, subsequently had a positive effect on the comprehensive development of civil law, the increase in its importance in social life, the strengthening and growth of its position in the ranks of the branches of law [4, 55-60]. The main task of this article is to analyze the concepts of contract and deal in civil law.

Deal-1) is a synonym for the concepts of contract, contract, International contract, convention in law. 2) the action of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the establishment, modification or abolition of civil rights and duties of citizens and legal entities under the CC [3, 84-87]. The deal can be one-sided, two-sided or multiple-sided. If the desire of one party is necessary and sufficient in accordance with the legislation or the agreement of the parties to conclude a deal, such a deal is a unilateral transaction. Deals are concluded in oral or written (simple or notarized) form. Deals related to land plots and other real estate (transfer to another person, mortgage, long-term lease, acceptance of inheritance, etc.) must be subject to state registration.

Article 8 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes that contracts are considered one of the grounds for the emergence of civil rights and duties between the parties. Article 353 of the civil code describes the concept of a contract, according to which the agreement of two or more persons on the creation, modification or termination of civil rights and duties is called a

contract [1]. Contracts are divided into contracts that are concluded for a fee and for free. The fee is paid by the property transferred by one party to the contracts concluded in return, money or property in exchange for the service made [2, 38-42]. For example, one party is forced to pay rent for temporary use because the landlord of the property uses it. Examples of contracts concluded for such a fee are purchase and sale, supply of products, exchange, contract and many other contracts. If a different rule does not come from the legislation, a contract is considered a contract concluded for a fee, unless a special understanding of the content-essence of the contract. And in a contract for free, one party, without receiving a fee in favor of another party, can transfer some property, perform some work. For example, under a donation agreement, the owner of the property gives his property to another person for free. For free use, interest-free debt contracts are also included in contracts that are concluded free of charge.

According to Article 101 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan deals-it is said of the actions of citizens and legal entities aimed at establishing, modifying or abolishing civil rights and duties. Deals can be one-party, two-party or multi-party (contracts) [1]. If the desire of one party is necessary and sufficient in accordance with the legislation or the agreement of the parties to conclude a deal, such deal is a unilateral agreement.

To conclude a contract, two parties (bilateral agreement) or more than three parties (multilateral agreement) must express a desire to agree. That is, deals can be concluded both unilaterally and vice versa, while contracts differ only in terms of bilateral or multilateral structure.

Conclusion. Taking all into account it can be concluded that the concepts of agreement and contract are important in civil law. The comparative analysis shows that there are a number of differences between contracts and agreements. Deals can be one-party, two-party or multi-party (contracts). If the desire of one party is necessary and sufficient in accordance with the legislation or the agreement of the parties to conclude a deal, such deal is a unilateral agreement. To conclude a contract, two parties (bilateral agreement) or more than three parties (multilateral agreement) must express a desire to agree. Deals can be concluded both unilaterally and vice versa, while contracts differ only in terms of bilateral or multilateral structure.

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